

New Year's Wishes

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It's time for a new year, and I think we are all ready for it! At least I am.

This is just a short post, with a ggplot2 holiday card wishing you all a better 2021 than 2020! Let's face it, there not much needed for that to happen, and with vaccines being distributed I have hopes.

I hope the New Year, at some point, makes it possible to start going to conferences again and that I can get to meet ore R-aficionados when the time allows.

As previous years, I wanted to make a holiday card for you all in ggplot2. You may ask why I keep plotting these ridiculous things in ggplot2, but the answer is quite simple: why not? Other than being fun, it's also a nice exercise in thinking about and exploring how data need to look to create a certain output. I find these holiday cards help me understand the geoms, how ggplot2 works, and how to think about grid structures.

Making a holiday card

The first thing I do when starting a new plot, is make sure I have a decent colour palette going. I browse through hex palettes for palettes I like, and this time a choose one called Chinese New Year - Rooster Color Palette, that I thought might work.

```
# Define a palette object
pal <- c("#f90000", "#9a1010", "#f4eb1a", "#e1d921", "#e79516")

# Have a look at the colours
scales::show_col(pal)
```


Next, I had in mind a simple image, with some blurred coloured circles in the background of some white text. So I had so make a data.frame with the basis of some circles. I knew I wanted to use `ggforce::geom_circle` for this, which would need x and y coordinates for the center of the circle and the radius. So I needed a data.frame with that information, and also a colour for each circle.

```
library(tidyverse)

# Choose the number of circles to make
n_circles <- 15

# Create data.frame with coordinate, radius and colour drawn by random.
circles <- tibble(
  x = sample(1:20, n_circles),
  y = sample(1:20, n_circles),
  r = sample(seq(.5, 1.5, length.out = 20), n_circles),
  c = sample(pal, n_circles, replace = TRUE)
)
```

circles

```
## # A tibble: 15 x 4
##       x     y     r c
##   <int> <int> <dbl> <chr>
## 1    14     3 1.18 #9a1010
## 2     1    13 0.816 #9a1010
## 3    17    19 1.29  #f90000
```

```
## 4 19 7 0.868 #f4eb1a
## 5 18 15 1.24 #e1d921
## 6 4 10 1.39 #f90000
## 7 3 2 0.605 #e1d921
## 8 9 6 1.08 #9a1010
## 9 12 11 1.03 #e1d921
## 10 2 8 0.5 #e79516
## 11 16 20 0.553 #f4eb1a
## 12 8 1 0.974 #f4eb1a
## 13 15 12 0.711 #f90000
## 14 20 4 0.763 #9a1010
## 15 11 5 1.5 #9a1010
```

After that, I needed to do some stuff to make the circles blurred. I've opted for a simple solution, where I'd overlay circles of decreasing sizes on top of each other with high transparency, which should look like a blurring effect. To achieve that, I decided to keep to my tibble and tidyverse way of doing things. First, I defined a separate tibble with the different sizes I want the radii to have for the blurring.

```
transp <- tibble(
  size = seq(from = 1, to = 1.9, length.out = 10)
)
transp
```

```
## # A tibble: 10 x 1
##   size
##   <dbl>
## 1 1
## 2 1.1
## 3 1.2
## 4 1.3
## 5 1.4
## 6 1.5
## 7 1.6
## 8 1.7
## 9 1.8
## 10 1.9
```

Using this, I needed to make sure that each circle (every row in the `circles` tibble) gets this blurring working. The best way I know how, is nesting the data by everything but radius, then merge the radius tibble with the transparency tibble, and unnest again. Lastly I can multiply the radius with the size, and get a large data.frame with lots of circles of different sizes, but many sharing a center and colour.

```
# Nesting data moved all non-grouped columns into a "data" column
circles %>%
  nest_by(x, y, c)
```

```
## # A tibble: 15 x 4
## # Rowwise: x, y, c
##   x     y c     data
##   <int> <int> <chr> <list<tbl_df[,1]>>
## 1     1     13 #9a1010 [1 x 1]
## 2     2     8 #e79516 [1 x 1]
## 3     3     2 #e1d921 [1 x 1]
## 4     4    10 #f90000 [1 x 1]
## 5     8     1 #f4eb1a [1 x 1]
## 6     9     6 #9a1010 [1 x 1]
```

```
## 7 11 5 #9a1010 [1 x 1]
## 8 12 11 #e1d921 [1 x 1]
## 9 14 3 #9a1010 [1 x 1]
## 10 15 12 #f90000 [1 x 1]
## 11 16 20 #f4eb1a [1 x 1]
## 12 17 19 #f90000 [1 x 1]
## 13 18 15 #e1d921 [1 x 1]
## 14 19 7 #f4eb1a [1 x 1]
## 15 20 4 #9a1010 [1 x 1]
```

Once the data is nested, the `radius` column is all alone, nested within the `data` column of the tibble. This way we can safely merge the `transp` object with that data, which will duplicate the radius number for every row in the `transp` object. Here, we must make sure that within the `mutate` the output of the merge is nested within a `list()`. The `data` column is a so-called list-column, and as such the output of any manipulation of it must also be a list.

```
# Merge the data column with the transp object,
# make sure it outputs into a list to work with nested data
circles %>%
  nest_by(x, y, c) %>%
  mutate(data = list(merge(data, transp)))
```

```
## # A tibble: 15 x 4
## # Rowwise: x, y, c
##       x     y c     data
##   <int> <int> <chr> <list>
## 1     1     13 #9a1010 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 2     2     8 #e79516 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 3     3     2 #e1d921 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 4     4    10 #f90000 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 5     8     1 #f4eb1a <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 6     9     6 #9a1010 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 7    11     5 #9a1010 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 8    12    11 #e1d921 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 9    14     3 #9a1010 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 10   15    12 #f90000 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 11   16    20 #f4eb1a <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 12   17    19 #f90000 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 13   18    15 #e1d921 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 14   19     7 #f4eb1a <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
## 15   20     4 #9a1010 <df[,2] [10 x 2]>
```

Once they are merged, we can `unnest` and see that our new `circles` object has lots of new rows!

```
# Unnest the data, so that a large tibble exposed (lots of rows!)
circles %>%
  nest_by(x, y, c) %>%
  mutate(data = list(merge(data, transp))) %>%
  unnest(data)
```

```
## # A tibble: 150 x 5
## # Groups:   x, y, c [15]
##       x     y c     r size
##   <int> <int> <chr> <dbl> <dbl>
## 1     1     13 #9a1010 0.816 1
## 2     1     13 #9a1010 0.816 1.1
## 3     1     13 #9a1010 0.816 1.2
```

```
## 4      1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.3
## 5      1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.4
## 6      1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.5
## 7      1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.6
## 8      1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.7
## 9      1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.8
## 10     1      13 #9a1010 0.816  1.9
## # ... with 140 more rows
```

Then the size column can be multiplied with the radius column, to get circles of different sizes.

```
# multiply r with the size to get the "true" radius.
circles <- circles %>%
  nest_by(x, y, c) %>%
  mutate(data = list(merge(data, transp))) %>%
  unnest(data) %>%
  mutate(r = r*size)
circles
```

```
## # A tibble: 150 x 5
## # Groups:   x, y, c [15]
##       x     y c         r size
##   <int> <int> <chr>  <dbl> <dbl>
## 1     1     1 13 #9a1010 0.816  1
## 2     1     1 13 #9a1010 0.897  1.1
## 3     1     1 13 #9a1010 0.979  1.2
## 4     1     1 13 #9a1010 1.06   1.3
## 5     1     1 13 #9a1010 1.14   1.4
## 6     1     1 13 #9a1010 1.22   1.5
## 7     1     1 13 #9a1010 1.31   1.6
## 8     1     1 13 #9a1010 1.39   1.7
## 9     1     1 13 #9a1010 1.47   1.8
## 10    1     1 13 #9a1010 1.55   1.9
## # ... with 140 more rows
```

Then it's all about plotting the data. Initially, I wanted a small animation like blinking of the circles, but I've decided to leave it as is for now.

Loading in ggforce, we get the `geom_circle` available. I'm also using a small colour hack a found a long time ago. When I have the colours in the data.frame directly, as it's own column, I usually use the identity function (`I()`) directly in the ggplot2 calls, rather than `scale_colour_identity`. It's just something I got used to.

```
library(ggforce)
alpha = .1

ggplot(circles, aes(fill = I(c))) +
  # Add all the circles
  geom_circle(alpha = .1, colour = NA,
             aes(x0 = x, y0 = y, r = r)) +
  # Add text at the center, but a little higher (+5)
  geom_text(aes(x = mean(circles$x),
               y = mean(circles$y)+5,
               label = "Happy New Year"),
           family = "Great Vibes",
           colour = "#fefefe",
           size = 14,
```

```
      show.legend = FALSE) +  
# Add text at the center but a little lower (-5)  
  geom_text(aes(x = mean(circles$x),  
                y = mean(circles$y)-5,  
                label = "Adios 2020!",  
                family = "Great Vibes",  
                size = 8,  
                colour = "#fefefe",  
                show.legend = FALSE) +  
theme_void() +  
theme(plot.background = element_rect(fill="black")) +  
NULL
```